

Study On The Influencing Factors And Promotion Strategies Of Higher Vocational Students' Learning Ability In The Information Age

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 01, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Influencing Factors , Promotion Strategies</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7600236</p>	<p><i>In the research on the study of higher vocational students' learning ability, the researchers mainly focus on the cultivation of learning ability and the analysis of the current situation. With the deepening of research and attention on vocational students' learning ability, learning ability plays a more and more significant role in the lifelong learning and future sustainable development of vocational college students. Higher vocational students learning ability training strategy research should be the focus of attention and research, the current research is mostly using the questionnaire survey students learning status and problems and put forward the corresponding training promotion method, the lack of related system of theoretical support, the future research focus should be based on time development, higher vocational colleges and students' thought and behavior characteristics, the scientific system related theory as guidance and support, discusses the path of system improve students learning method, in order to better improve higher vocational colleges to cultivate innovative practice skills talent education effect.</i></p>

Introduction

Learning power originated in the field of organizational management. As for the word learning ability, the explanation given in teaming (Double Solution of American Traditional Dictionary) is the teamwork ability between learners, which emphasizes that learning ability exists in group organizations and is a kind of team learning ability. The origin of the core idea of retrospective learning is from the founder of Systems Dynamics MIT J.W. Professor Forrester proposed for the first time, so the academic community agreed that the concept of learning ability was first produced in the theory of organizational management. J.W. Professor Forrester pointed out that learning ability is a combination of individual learning attitude and learning ability demonstrated in the process of lifelong learning, which can be divided into individual learning ability and organizational team learning ability. He takes learning ability and perseverance as the most basic element of individual learning ability, and also the most critical element of individual learning ability. though J.W. Professor Forrester did not give a detailed explanation of the meaning of learning ability, but he affirmed its important role and significance in the organization and management. Later, his student, management guru Peter M. Senge made an in-depth study on the theory of learning ability, and discussed the problems related to learning ability in his masterpiece the Fifth Discipline, and in J.W. Forrester On the basis of the research, three elements of learning ability, namely learning ability, learning perseverance and learning motivation. Under the guidance of the theory constructed by him, it fully mobilized the learning ability of the enterprise members, helped the world-famous enterprises to find effective methods to break through the bottleneck of long-term development, and promoted the long-term sustainable development of the enterprise.

Learning ability develops in the field of pedagogy. With the deepening of research, more and more learning power was used for reference by educational scholars. In the 1980s, Kirby (W.C. Kirby) (Harvard University) studied "learning ability" in the field of education, and further discussed and studied the problem of learning ability in his work of Learning Power. He emphasized that learning ability is a comprehensive ability to mobilize other factors. Later, the learning ability has been further studied in students, teachers, subjects and other aspects, and is widely used in the education field. Subsequently, the concept of "learning ability" appeared in the Japanese education circle, which is very similar to the concept of "learning ability". From the perspective of adolescent learning, it is defined as a concept of developmental explicit growth, which specifically refers to the ability and level of "learning" gradually cultivated in the long-term learning. This paper holds that the connotation of "learning ability" and "learning ability" is not exactly the same, and "learning ability" is the ability and level of learners to absorb and internalize the acquired knowledge, skills and apply them flexibly and creatively on the basis of using the original knowledge structure. On the basis of integrating existing knowledge and using new knowledge ability, the ability and level of trying to change their current and future learning life and working state should be the focus of "learning ability".

After the study of learning organization gradually, more and more attention to learning, and by the attention of many experts and scholars, in order to realize the purpose of lifelong learning and improve learners learning for the research content and focus, gradually become an important management theory of knowledge economy, and gradually in the field of education.

At the end of the 20th century, China began to introduce the concept of learning ability. Professor Zhong Qiquan was the first one to study learning ability and mention the concept of learning ability. He believed that learning ability included the basis of learning ability, basic learning ability, and developmental learning ability (creative learning ability).

Yu Jianxiang, as an education expert in China, is the first person to conduct systematic research on learning ability. In his years of education practice research, he studied the relevant learning case at home and abroad and learn from the relevant academic theory on the basis of the happy fast learning method, gradually formed a relatively complete learning education system, he combined education teaching practice, created the learning habits, learning mind, learning methods, learning management, learning motivation, learning will learning "six elements". Although his research is more applicable to primary and secondary school education, it also has important practical significance and reference value, which can play a good role in helping and guiding the learning efficiency and learning ability of primary and secondary school students, thus pushing the relevant educational research of learning ability from the theoretical level to the application field and made great progress.

With the development of the era of knowledge economy, the concept of "lifelong learning" has been continuously popularized, and it has become an important concept to enhance the comprehensive competitiveness of individuals and even the country. For the development and progress of the country and the nation, it is necessary to create a good learning atmosphere and insist on continuous learning and practice. Therefore, the study of learning ability has become the meaning of the construction of a "learning society".

In the 2015 "International Learning Power Summit Forum", Professor Nicholas Negroponte once mentioned that learning power has become the most important ability of human beings, and redesigning learning will be the most important mission of education. Professor Ren Youqun of China also put forward the concept of "national learning power", that is, to use information technology to achieve the goal of expanding the knowledge flow, expanding the total amount of knowledge and optimizing the quality of knowledge, so as to realize the accelerated update of information and knowledge.

In conclusion, the study of learning has experienced from the field of organization management to psychology, pedagogy, from abroad to domestic gradually expand and rich course, in recent years, also constantly become the research of college education workers, therefore, learning research on education development, national social progress has an important role and value.

The source of learning power

Everyone's development is inseparable from learning, and they should constantly improve their ability by actively or passively acquiring relevant knowledge or experience. Where does the learning power come from exactly? Are we born with it or are we acquired in practice? This paper analyzes and combs out relevant literature and summarizes the following views on the source of learning ability.

One view is that learning ability is innate to learning individuals. For example, Ma Ying (2013) holds this view in her research on the learning ability of primary school students. She defines the nature of learning ability by the basic cultural quality, and advocates that learners' learning state and learning behavior can be improved through their own innate learning ability, and constantly stimulate and promote their own learning potential. Learning ability is a necessary ability for individuals to learn in their lifelong learning career development.

The other view, on the contrary, is that learning ability is acquired through practical exercise. For example, Guo Weili (2012) believes that learners' learning ability is gradually formed in the process of theoretical learning and practice. She defines the nature of learning power from the perspective of forming a learner development system. She proposed that learning ability can stimulate the important power of learning individual potential, which is not only reflected in the ability to acquire, practice and create knowledge, but also in changing the knowledge and spirit of learners. Chen Weiwei, Yang Huan (2010) Through the study of learning ability in the field of education, they proposed that learning ability is the emergence and continuous improvement of learning individuals in the process of learning, life activities and practice. On this basis, it is proposed that learning power is the abstract existence of human carrier.

This paper holds that the formation of innate learning ability is related to the basic cultural literacy and knowledge reserve, and the learning ability is based on the original cultural literacy and knowledge reserve, and through the acquired theoretical learning accumulation and learning practice, in the continuous stimulation of their own learning potential. In any case, the function process of learning power is from learning to learning, so as to encourage learners to constantly break through themselves and create the dynamic process of using new knowledge.

The connotation research of learning power

Through the above analysis of the development process of learning ability, most of the research on learning ability at home and abroad starts from both basic and practical applied research. In addition, the early basic theoretical research is mostly the discussion of the connotation and elements of learning ability, while the practical application research is mainly reflected in how to cultivate and improve the learning ability. In this part, the relevant research on the concept and connotation of learning ability is mainly based on the two aspects of foundation and practical application.

Early people in the field of organizational management as the combination of ability, motivation and perseverance. It was widely noticed from the late 20th century and became a popular research subject. It is generally believed in education circles that the connotation of learning power is different from the elements. In recent years, the majority of scholars at home and abroad on the interpretation and definition of the connotation of learning power show a hundred schools of thought contend.

Foreign scholars generally regard the combination of learning motivation, perseverance, ability and innovation as learning ability, which is the overall skill presented by learners in the process of acquiring, sharing, applying and creating knowledge. As example, Peter M. Professor Senge (1994) at J.W. Forrester Professor on the basis of research, learning ability is formed in the process of learning new learning cognition and learning behavior process, namely after learning will generate new behavior, which broke the learning ability to gain and use the traditional meaning of knowledge, understand it as a new behavior and new thinking, realize the process of self innovation. Professor Kirby (2005) is here in Peter M. Senge On the basis of his research, Professor He refines the concept of learning ability by interpreting the elements of learning ability. In the book Learning Ability, he points out that learning ability consists of learning attitude, learning efficiency, learning style, learning perseverance and innovation ability. In essence, it is the process and ability to obtain innovation results. William Kirby (2005) proposed that the learning ability of learners can be generated and improved in the process of development, progress and acquisition of knowledge. Crick R D, Claxton G (2004) believes that learning ability is an ideology that integrates with unique attitude, personality and values. He proposed that building learning ability and developing migratory ability to make people become better learners, and constantly promote lifelong learning ability. Michael Jetx (B.J. McGettrick) (2002) In the theory of "double spiral structure", learning ability first reflects the learning intention, values, emotion and learning motivation of learners; second, learning ability reflects the results and goals of expected acquired knowledge, understanding and skills. Konica (R.D. Crick) (2006) believes on the basis of the double helix structure theory that the energy that integrates the interaction of learning willingness and learning outcomes is learning power.

Domestic scholars have discussed the concept of learning ability mainly from the aspects of knowledge acquisition, application, transformation and innovation. This paper combs and summarizes them in the form of a table, as shown in the following table.

Table 1 represents scholars' opinions on the connotation of learning ability

Representative scholars	The connotation of learning power
Sultanan (1997)	People's learning experience and learning ability are gradually formed in their daily study, life and work.
Gu Kunhua (2003)	Learning ability is the synthesis of individual lifelong learning and learning attitude and ability, and is the overall performance of the total amount, quality, stock, flow and increment of learning.
Jiang Wenzhao (2006)	
Wu Yongjun (2004)	Enterprise learning ability is the development ability of the enterprise organization to overcome the forward resistance through "learning" and maintain its own future advantages.
Li Dejin (2004)	Learning ability is the ability to quickly transform the acquired new knowledge resources into knowledge capital.
Wu Gaofei (2006)	The term "learning ability" is first the concept of psychology, which mainly refers to the individual learning ability of individuals. People are used to use the professional term "learning ability" in the field of pedagogy, that is, learning the ability of individuals to constantly change their own life, learning and working state in the process of acquiring and applying knowledge.
Peng Xilin (2007)	Based on the study of individual and organizational learning ability, he believes that learning ability is a variety of intellectual skills formed in the process of organizing learning activities, learning and application of new knowledge.
Liu Binxiang (2007)	Learning ability is the ability of learning individuals to realize self-innovation and constantly improve their own survival and development state in the continuous access to information.
Wu Taisheng	In the broad sense, learning ability can be understood as the sum of skills to

- (2007) acquire knowledge attitude and ability by different means and methods, which is the comprehensive embodiment of learners' learning motivation and ability system, knowledge background and knowledge level; in the narrow sense, learning ability, motivation and perseverance of learning ability, also known as discipline learning ability.
- Qu Jing (2008) Learning ability is a dynamic ability system to improve learning ability through external environment, self-reflection and practice on the basis of acquiring knowledge and skills in the learning process.
- Liu Hongying (2008) Learning ability is the ability of learners to constantly improve themselves in the process of utilizing and creating knowledge.
- Gu Li (2009) Learning ability is the psychological quality of personality presented in learning activities.
- Liu Lei (2011) Learning ability is the ability to constantly discover, analyze and solve problems in learning practice with understanding as the core. The complete connotation of learning ability can be understood as: the subject of learning ability is human, the core and essence of learning ability is understanding, the external performance of learning ability is the formation of new behaviors after learning, and the result of learning ability is viability, development ability, competitiveness and innovation.
- Zhou JiuJun (2011) Learning ability is the sum total of learning motivation, learning perseverance, learning ability, learning efficiency and learning innovation. It is the ability of people to acquire and share the application and create knowledge.
- Xu Peiqing (2011) Learning ability is the abbreviation of people's comprehensive learning ability, is the unique potential ability of people, is the comprehensive performance of learning motivation, learning ability, learning method effectiveness, learning perseverance, learning innovation vitality and learning potential, is the key index to measure the learning level of learners.
- He Wuhua (2013) A comprehensive system of various power factors that support learners' continuous learning.
- Zheng Weibo, Sun (2013) The study of learning ability should not be limited to the scope of its ability, but should be a state, a survival mode manifested through the behavior of the learning subject. Learning ability is a dynamic system in which the learning subject uses his ability accumulated in all aspects in the long-term learning process, constantly discover, acquire, apply and transform knowledge through continuous learning and efforts, and finally transform it into its own comprehensive quality improvement and a subtle influence on the external environment.
- Mingshuai (2013)
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- Pendina (2016) Learning ability is the growth ability, vitality and growth energy of students.
- Chen Kun (2018) Learning ability is a dynamic ability system to promote the continuous improvement of learning character, and is a real measure to measure a person's comprehensive quality and competitiveness.
- Wang Fei, Zhang Yan (2018) Learning ability is a comprehensive element system that supports students to learn and complete learning goals or achieve the construction of new things. Learning ability consists of three elements: intelligent elements, non-intelligent elements, and practical support elements.
- Zhu Hongying (2019) It is believed that the connotation of learning power and its components are a complex complex, and the learning power is not determined by a single factor, but is produced in the process of mutual influence and interaction with the environment.

Source: This article is collated

Shi Jianjun (2017) summarized the research on learning ability in the field of education, and sorted out six viewpoints on the connotation of learning power, representative scholars: ELLI project, Wu Yixian, Diao Peixia, Jiang Wenzhao, ability view and representatives: Xu Peiqing, Qu Jing; energy view, representative scholars: British R.D.Crick and Shen Shusheng; quality view, Gu Li; development concept; comprehensive system view, professor Kirby of Harvard University, He Wuhua, etc.

Through the analysis, it is found that due to the different disciplines of researchers' own research fields, the grasp and analysis of the connotation of learning power is relatively scattered, and there is no clear definition of the connotation. On this basis, this paper summarizes that the learning power has some common points in comprehensiveness and complexity: First, the learning power exists objectively. Although it is an invisible and abstract existence, but it is a real existence produced in people's learning, understanding and practical activities. Secondly, the subject of learning power is human beings, which is attached to people. Learning ability is a process related to the learning activities of the learning subject in the formation of human learning practice

activities and the ability improvement through the achievement of learning goals and the change of learning behavior. Thirdly, the development of learning ability is a process from learning to learning, which is usually manifested in comprehensive learning ability. It is a process of reprocessing and innovation of knowledge, information, experience, skills and so on, which can be improved through certain ways. Finally, from the perspective of results and external performance, the result of learning ability is the improvement of the comprehensive learning ability, and the improvement of the potential sustainable learning ability to acquire new knowledge and transform innovation.

Through the above analysis, this paper believes that learning is generally produced in human learning activities and enterprise or organization development, it is not only constrained by the ability of this scope, learning should be a living state of sustainable development, reflected in all aspects, such as study, life, work, so, learning power should be broad and narrow sense. In the broad sense, learning ability refers to the learning competitiveness and innovation ability of social groups or organizations, while in the narrow sense, learning ability refers to the individual (student) learning ability. It is the dynamic development process of acquiring knowledge, reorganizing and updating knowledge, creating new knowledge, applying new knowledge, transforming new knowledge, reproducing new knowledge, reorganizing and updating knowledge, and creating new knowledge... thus constantly changing the ability of life, work and learning. This paper discusses the learning ability of higher vocational college students. Due to the particularity of their learning and employment, we should focus more on the performance of learning ability, such as learning ability and learning adaptability. People's learning ability is related to knowledge reserve, cognitive level and practical ability. Learning ability focuses more on the ability of learning something, applying what they learn and learning to innovate. Therefore, learning ability is a kind of sustainable survival competitiveness, especially for the creation, regeneration and transformation ability of knowledge and skills, which is measured by the improvement of learning ability, thinking ability, practical ability and innovation ability.

Research on the components of learning ability

This paper holds that the constituent elements and connotation of learning power are interrelated and different concepts, the connotation of learning power is the definition and interpretation of the concept of learning power itself, and the constituent elements of learning power are an important component shown by the subject of learning force in the specific learning practice activities. Most researchers usually analyze the learning ability by using the analysis of the components of the learning ability. Among them, the more representative views in these aspects mainly include "four elements", "six elements", "seven elements", "complex theory" and so on. This paper combs and summarizes the representative views of scholars on this issue, as shown in the table below.

Table 2 represents scholars' research on the elements of learning ability

Representative scholars	inscape
Hiroyo Inaba, Japan (1994)	Learning ability consists of three elements: emotional cognition and skill.
Sultan (1997)	Learning experience, learning ability
Claxton (2002)	Four elements say: compliance force, policy stress, reflection force, mutual benefit force.
Gao Zhimin (2002)	The components of learning ability are divided into the activation ability and learning ability of learning activities, the understanding ability and total motivation of learning behavior, the recognition ability of learning needs, and the evaluation ability of learning potential.
Kirby (2005)	Learning ability includes learning motivation, learning attitude, learning method, learning efficiency, innovative thinking and creativity.
UK ELLI Project (2006)	Seven elements say: change and learning, with critical curiosity, meaning construction, creativity, learning reciprocity, strategic awareness, and compliance force.
Chen Manlin Xue-jiao zhang Zhong Zhixian, Angel Lin (2008)	The main elements of learning ability include learning transformation ability, learning efficiency, learning motivation, perseverance and ability.
Representative scholars	inscape
Liu Bin details, Zou Yajie Jian (2007)	Learning power consists of three elements: willpower, goal and experience.
Peng Xilin (2007)	Learning ability mainly includes the ability to organize and apply knowledge and the relevant intellectual skills acquired in the

	process.
Liu Yonghe (2009)	Learning ability has the four elements of learning motivation, ability, perseverance and creativity.
Wu Zhenli (2011)	Learning motivation, learning perseverance and learning ability.
Zheng Weibo, Sun Mingshuai (2013)	The elements of learning ability include understanding and thinking, initiative and persistence, cooperation and sharing, exploration and innovation, application and transformation, feedback and improvement.
He Wuhua (2013)	Power system, behavior system, regulating system, environmental support system.
Light Xia (2014)	The main elements of learning ability include learning cooperation ability, reflection ability and learning efficiency.
Pendina (2016)	Learning ability consists of three levels of basic quality, self-development and the highest level, and related six elements.
Learning Power Project Team of Jinan Education and Teaching Research Institute (2017)	Learning ability is understood as students' learning ability, which mainly include learning motivation (willing to learn), learning interest (happy learning), learning methods (learning), learning habits (learning) and learning creativity (good learning).
Jiang Zhihui, Zhao Chengling, et al. (2017)	Learning ability includes five aspects: learning motivation, learning perseverance, learning ability, learning reciprocity and learning creativity.
Wang Fei, Zhang Yan (2018)	Learning ability consists of three elements: first, intelligent elements, which take learning ability as the core, such as knowledge construction ability, learning monitoring ability, learning ability, and innovation ability; second, non-intelligent elements, such as learning motivation, learning perseverance, learning interest, learning attitude, and third, practice support elements, such as learning Movement, learning atmosphere, learning reward system, etc. The key to the cultivation of learning ability focuses on the intelligent elements with learning ability as the core, and the non-intelligent elements are the premise, and the practical support elements are the guarantee.

Source: collation of this study

Chen Weiwei (2010) believes that foreign scholars mainly use qualitative and quantitative research methods, questionnaire survey and data statistics to analyze the components of learning ability for people of different ages. Most scholars in China focus on personal theory analysis and construction. A comprehensive comparison of domestic and foreign scholars on the elements of learning ability mainly presents different perspectives of education, physics, management, system theory, psychology and philosophy.

In this paper, it is found that most of the theoretical viewpoints of the constituent elements of learning power are mainly focused on three perspectives: pedagogy, psychology and physics. For example, Chen Manlin, Zhang Xuejiao, Zheng Weibo, Wu Zhenli and other scholars mainly study the elements of learning ability from the perspective of pedagogy, mainly from the sustainable development of the learning process, Hiroba, Gao Zhimin and Zou Yajun mainly study the elements of learning ability from the psychological perspective; Peng Xilin studies the elements of learning ability from the perspective of physics, mainly from the learning process. Although domestic and foreign scholars have different perspectives on the research of learning ability and the division of the components of learning ability, they basically keep the same in the perspective of division, basically from the perspective of —— learners, the subject of learning activities. It can be seen that most scholars agree that the components of learning ability are the important supporting factors to ensure or promote the smooth and efficient progress of learning activities and the learning process.

Conclusion

From the perspective of research foothold, most scholars' research on the learning ability of higher vocational students mainly discusses the improvement of learning ability from the macro theoretical level. The foothold of the research are different, the proposed theories are relatively scattered and not systematic enough, and the proposed methods and strategies lack certain practical teaching test. There are a few scholars from the practical level to explore, such as: Jin Rui, Ren Wen Yuan, Lin (2021) is put forward by combining the actual situation of higher vocational colleges to build network learning platform to improve the students' learning ability, from the platform characteristics, platform function design, platform module design put forward the implementation plan of building network learning platform. Yan Meng (2021), based on the status quo of

learning ability of college students 'work, proposed to carry out training camps to improve college students through the specific implementation process of counselors. After verification through practice, he has made certain achievements in school spirit, network ideological and political education, and counselors' professional ability.

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